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Influence of the Gomti River in Enhancing Lucknow's Commercial Sector: A Spatial Case Study of Lucknow City, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract

The Gomti River, originating from Gomat Taal in Madho Tanda, holds significant cultural, ecological, and economic value in Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh. This perennial river flows through the city, facilitating diverse functions, including drinking water supply, irrigation, and local navigation. However, its impact on Lucknow's commercial sector remains an underexplored yet critical subject. The riverfront and surrounding areas are hubs of economic activities such as farming, boating, tourism, water extraction, and vending. These activities not only generate employment but also contribute to the city's commercial vibrancy. Moreover, key landmarks like bridges and temples along the Gomti attract tourists and vendors, adding to the economic potential of the region.

Despite its economic benefits, the Gomti River faces significant challenges, primarily pollution caused by human and industrial activities along its banks. This study examines the spatial dimensions of the Gomti River's influence on Lucknow's commercial sector, exploring how economic activities interact with and impact the river's health. Using geospatial tools and field surveys, the research identifies key areas of commercial dependence on the river and assesses the balance between economic gains and environmental sustainability.

The findings highlight the necessity of sustainable management practices to preserve the Gomti River while maximizing its economic benefits. The study advocates for policy measures that integrate ecological conservation with urban and commercial planning to ensure the long-term viability of the Gomti as a natural and economic resource.

Key Words: Commercial sector, spatial analysis, riverfront development, sustainable management, economic activities, tourism, urban planning, pollution.

Introduction

Rivers have historically been vital for sustenance and movement, offering food, clean water, and fertile floodplains for agriculture, which gave rise to great river valley civilizations. Over time, rivers became essential for navigation, trade, and cultural exchange. With towns and industries developing along riverbanks, they became hubs of economic activity but also sites of significant exploitation. Industrial units often use river water for manufacturing and discharge untreated waste, altering pH levels, increasing temperatures, and disrupting aquatic ecosystems. Today, most rivers are heavily polluted. The Gomti River in Lucknow, impacted by unregulated commercial activities, urgently requires preservation and restoration efforts.

The Gomti River Basin spans between 79°57'–83°11' E longitudes and 25°23'–28°42' N latitudes, covering an area of 31,433.67 sq. km. Dividing Lucknow into Trans-Gomti and Cis-Gomti regions, the basin borders the Ramganga Basin (northwest), Ghaghara Basin (north/northeast), and Ganga Basin (south/southeast). It comprises three sub-basins: Upper Gomti, Lower Gomti, and Sai. Originating near Mainkot from Gomat Taal (Fulhar Jheel) in Madhotanda, Pilibhit, at 185 m elevation, the Gomti River flows 940 km through districts like Sitapur, Lucknow, Sultanpur, and Jaunpur before joining the Ganges at Kaithi, Ghazipur. Its major tributary, River Sai, drains 12,900 sq. km. The basin, characterized by Quaternary alluvial sediments, experiences a subtropical monsoonal climate with distinct dry winters, hot summers, and rainy monsoons.

Figure 1: Map of Lucknow

Source: <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:LucknowMap.PNG>

Lucknow is a thriving hub for wholesale and retail trade, serving as a key regional market for food grains, agricultural products, and various goods sourced from its hinterland. Prominent commercial areas such as Hazratganj, Aminabad, and Chowk have a rich history of over 150 years, while newer markets like Nishatganj, Gomti Nagar, Kapoorthala, and Indira Nagar host corporate offices, service units, shopping malls, restaurants, educational institutions, and more. Major wholesale markets include Dubagga, Yahiyaganj, Fatehganj, Pandeyganj, and Daliganj, primarily dealing in food grains and vegetables.

Interestingly, approximately 5% of Lucknow's population, or 1.5 million people, work in the informal sector, far exceeding the typical 2-2.5% in urban areas. These street vendors operate through stalls, hawking services, and weekly markets across the city, with notable ones held in Alambagh, Nishatganj, Aminabad, and Sadar. Despite their economic contribution, they lack designated trading spaces and rely on mobility.

While significant research explores industrial impacts on river ecosystems, the role of rivers in supporting economic activities is underexplored. This study examines the economic dependence of Lucknow residents on the Gomti River, shedding light on its role as a center for informal commercial exchanges and how it supports livelihoods.

Table 1: Weekly Markets in Lucknow

Day of the Week	Market Place
Tuesday	Alambagh
Wednesday	Nishatganj
Thursday	Aminabad & Nazirabad
Saturday	Sadar
Sunday	Nakkas Chauk

Source: Revised City Development Plan of Lucknow City, 2015

Objectives

This study aims to examine the role of the Gomti River in supporting commercial economic activities in Lucknow and to evaluate the impact of these activities on the river's condition.

The specific objectives of the research are:

- To assess the contribution of the Gomti River to the commercial economic activities in Lucknow.
- To evaluate the impact of these commercial activities on the ecological health of the Gomti River in Lucknow.

Data and Methodology

For carrying out the present study quantitative research methodology was adopted. For obtaining primary data a questionnaire survey consisting of 21 questions was circulated among 100 participants. All the participants were residents of Lucknow keeping in view their familiarity with River Gomti. The questions were related to the importance of River Gomti in supporting the economic activities of commercial nature in Lucknow city and the effect they have on the river. Probability sampling technique was used to select the sample population. Different research papers and articles were also reviewed to obtain secondary data relating to the study.

Result

The Gomti River, flowing through the city of Lucknow, has evolved into a vital asset for various commercial activities, making it an essential resource for the local economy. The river's presence is intricately tied to the lives of people living along its banks, where the water and the infrastructure surrounding it serve as critical components for farming, dairy

activities, tourism, and other commercial enterprises. However, while these economic benefits are significant, the increased exploitation of the river's resources has led to environmental challenges that threaten its long-term sustainability.

Commercial Activities Dependent on the River's Water and Infrastructure

The Gomti River plays an important role in supporting agriculture, particularly in areas such as Ghaila village, where farmers rely on its water for irrigation. Farmers in these regions divert water from the river to irrigate their fields, growing a variety of crops that are sold in local markets. This form of irrigation offers an affordable and accessible means for farmers to sustain their livelihoods, making the river an invaluable resource for agriculture. The use of river water for irrigation helps keep farming costs low, enabling farmers to invest in other areas of their business.

In addition to agriculture, dairy farming along the riverbanks benefits from the river's free access to water and natural vegetation. Dairy farmers graze their cattle along the river, providing them with an ample water supply and reducing the need to purchase feed. The river's vegetation serves as a natural food source for the animals, making the river a crucial resource for the dairy industry in the region.

The river also supports a variety of recreational and tourism activities, including boating. At sites such as Hanumat Dham, Lallumal Ghat, and Kudiya Ghat, boatmen earn a living by offering boat rides to locals and tourists alike. The cost of a boat ride varies depending on the duration and number of passengers but typically starts around ₹250. Boating has become increasingly popular, especially among tourists and locals looking to enjoy scenic views of the river. The growing trend of pre-wedding photoshoots has further contributed to the rise in tourism, as couples flock to these picturesque locations to capture memorable moments by the river. This trend has created an additional source of income for boatmen, who cater to the rising demand for recreational and aesthetic photography along the river.

Another significant commercial use of the river is the extraction of water for household and agricultural purposes. Water from the river is pumped and distributed to residents in nearby areas, providing them with an essential water supply. In addition, the river's water is channeled into canals for irrigation, supporting local farming activities. This extraction, while beneficial to local communities, adds pressure on the river's water levels, particularly during dry periods when water availability becomes scarce.

Commercial Activities Based on the River's Infrastructure

The infrastructure around the Gomti River, such as bridges and riverfront developments, plays an equally important role in supporting local commerce. For instance, the Hanman Setu bridge has become a bustling marketplace, with vendors selling a variety of goods, including fruits, vegetables, and snacks. These vendors make use of the bridge's high foot traffic, providing them with a steady income as people cross the bridge throughout the day. This kind of commerce contributes significantly to the local economy, offering small-scale entrepreneurs an opportunity to earn a livelihood.

The development of the Gomti Riverfront has also boosted tourism in the region. This area has become a popular destination for locals and tourists, offering various attractions such as restaurants, cultural sites, and recreational spaces. One area of particular note is Chatori Gali, located near the riverfront, which has become a hotspot for street food vendors. These vendors offer a wide range of local delicacies, drawing large crowds and generating revenue. The popularity of the riverfront and its associated businesses has led to increased job opportunities in the food service, hospitality, and retail sectors.

Religious activities along the Gomti River also contribute to local commerce. Several temples are situated along the river, such as Hanumat Dham, Chandrika Devi, and Hanuman Setu. These temples attract large numbers of devotees, who come to perform rituals and offer prayers. The surrounding areas are lined with shops and stalls selling religious items such as flowers, incense, and coconuts. These commercial activities, driven by religious tourism, provide a steady income for shopkeepers and vendors catering to the needs of temple-goers.

Environmental Impact of Commercial Activities

While the river provides essential resources for these various commercial activities, the environmental consequences are becoming increasingly apparent. One major concern is the pollution caused by agricultural runoff. Farmers often use fertilizers and pesticides in their crops, and when these chemicals are washed into the river, they contaminate the water, leading to nutrient overload. Excess nutrients like phosphorus and nitrogen can promote the growth of algae, leading to eutrophication and other water quality problems that harm aquatic life and make the water unsafe for consumption.

Another environmental challenge is the free access that dairy animals have to the river. Cattle often graze along the riverbanks, and their waste, combined with the pollutants from their hooves, contributes to the contamination of the water. This unregulated interaction between livestock and the river further accelerates the degradation of the river's ecosystem.

Boating activities, while economically beneficial, also contribute to pollution. Passengers sometimes discard waste such as plastic bottles, food wrappers, and other debris into the river, adding to the overall pollution load. The growing trend of pre-wedding photoshoots along the river also contributes to environmental harm. Items used for decoration during these photoshoots, such as flower petals and other materials, are often discarded into the water, further polluting the river.

Street food vendors, especially those located on the bridges and around the riverfront, contribute to the pollution of the Gomti River as well. Waste generated from food wrappers, plastic bags, and other items is often discarded into the river, either by vendors or by customers. This accumulation of waste, if not properly managed, leads to a gradual decline in the water quality.

Finally, religious practices, particularly the immersion of idols and ceremonial items, contribute to pollution. Devotees often immerse idols made of non-biodegradable materials into the river, which increases the sediment load and introduces harmful chemicals into the water. The organic waste from flowers and other ritual items also decomposes in the water, leading to unpleasant odors and further pollution.

Survey Findings on Commercial and Environmental Aspects

A survey conducted among 100 participants provides valuable insights into the commercial and environmental impacts of the Gomti River. The survey revealed that 36% of respondents confirmed that vegetables are grown along the riverbanks, while 63% acknowledged that the river's water is used for agricultural purposes. Additionally, 84% of respondents confirmed that dairy animals graze along the riverbanks, and 75% of them recognized that these animals contribute to water pollution.

Boating emerged as a widely recognized commercial activity, with 72% of respondents agreeing that it plays a significant role in the river's economy. A large majority, 93%, acknowledged that tourism, particularly adventure tourism and photography, has contributed to the river's economic significance. However, environmental concerns were also highlighted, with 86% of respondents aware of the pollution caused by idol immersions and religious rituals.

Discussion

The Gomti River is a vital geographical and cultural feature in Lucknow, sustaining the local economy through various commercial activities. The river serves as a critical resource, facilitating income generation across multiple sectors, while also facing significant environmental challenges due to these very activities. Insights gathered from a survey of 100 participants highlight the river's economic importance as well as the negative environmental impact of its commercial use.

In Ghaila Village, the river's water is utilized for agricultural purposes, particularly vegetable cultivation along the riverbanks. These vegetables are sold in local markets, contributing to the livelihoods of small-scale farmers and boosting the local economy. According to the survey, 63% of respondents consider the river water suitable for irrigation, while 37% disagree. However, 36% supported the practice of growing vegetables along the river, while 64% did not, suggesting diverse opinions on the river's capacity to support sustainable agriculture.

Apart from agriculture, the river is a crucial resource for the dairy sector. Dairy animals such as cows, buffaloes, and goats graze along the riverbanks and drink its water. The survey found that 84% of respondents had seen these animals, but concerns about water quality were evident, with 57% disagreeing that the river water is safe for consumption by livestock. Despite these concerns, the river continues to serve the needs of dairy farmers.

Tourism, particularly boating, has become a major source of income for many locals. The boatmen at locations like Lallumal Ghat and Kudiya Ghat earn money from tourists who pay for boat rides, with the river offering scenic views. The survey revealed that 72% of respondents recognized boating as an important commercial activity, and 93% acknowledged the growth in tourism, especially due to adventure and pre-wedding photoshoots. These activities have provided a unique source of livelihood for locals involved in photography, boating, and tourism-related services.

The river also plays an essential role in the city's irrigation system. Water from the river is pumped to supply nearby canals, benefiting agriculture. While 55% of survey respondents acknowledged this contribution, only 41% confirmed that water is pumped directly from the river for other purposes, indicating that the river's role in supporting the irrigation system is still debated.

The bridges that span the Gomti River are hubs of informal commerce. Vendors selling fruits, vegetables, and snacks along these bridges provide a livelihood for many, contributing to the local economy. The survey showed that 86% of respondents had observed these vendors. Additionally, the development of the Gomti Riverfront has further promoted tourism, with 92% of respondents believing it has boosted the local economy. The riverfront attracts both tourists and locals, and street food vendors, such as those in Chatori Gali, benefit from the influx of visitors. A majority of respondents (76%) visited the riverfront, recognizing its growing importance.

Temples along the Gomti River, such as those at Chandrika Devi, Hanuman Setu, and Hanumat Dham, also play a role in generating income. Devotees purchase offerings from local vendors, providing them with a source of income. According to the survey, 83% of respondents visited these temples, and 95% believed the temples have increased tourism, further contributing to the local economy.

However, the river's increasing commercialization has led to significant environmental concerns. Pollution has become a major issue, with waste disposal from temple rituals and other commercial activities negatively impacting the river. The survey revealed that 86% of respondents had witnessed the immersion of flowers and idols in the river, contributing to its pollution. Despite efforts by temple authorities to manage waste, 81% of respondents felt that pollution control was insufficient. Littering at the Gomti Riverfront was common, with 96% of respondents reporting such behavior. Furthermore, 75% of respondents noted that dairy animals contribute to pollution by releasing waste into the river.

To address these environmental issues, several measures can be implemented. Remote sensing technologies, such as infrared photography, can be used to monitor agricultural runoff and identify sources of pollution. Color infrared photography could help detect areas of eutrophication and monitor the health of aquatic vegetation. Additionally, relocating farming activities away from the riverbanks and providing alternative freshwater sources to farmers would help reduce pollution.

Encouraging dairy farmers to keep their animals away from the riverbanks and provide them with dedicated grazing spaces and clean water would also prevent further water contamination. Boatmen should be encouraged to use nets to remove any waste generated during boat rides. Similarly, vendors along the bridges and riverfront should be mandated to dispose of waste properly, preventing litter from accumulating. Street food vendors in Chatori Gali should provide waste bins and ensure that their stalls are left clean after use. Public education campaigns should encourage visitors to the riverfront to dispose of waste responsibly.

Temple authorities should implement waste management systems, such as composting organic waste from rituals and separating inorganic waste for proper disposal. Smaller idols could be immersed in controlled environments to minimize pollution, while larger idols should be placed in specially designed tanks to reduce their environmental impact.

Finally, a public awareness campaign should be launched to emphasize the importance of preserving the Gomti River. This campaign should highlight the environmental and economic value of the river and encourage collective action to protect it for future generations. By balancing the commercial benefits with sustainable environmental practices, the Gomti River can continue to serve as an important resource for Lucknow's residents and economy.

Conclusion:

The Gomti River plays an integral role in the economy and daily life of Lucknow, supporting a wide range of economic activities from agriculture to tourism. However, its ecological health has been significantly compromised by pollution, largely due to agricultural runoff, waste from livestock, littering, and religious practices. While these activities provide livelihoods for local communities, they pose a serious threat to the river's sustainability.

To preserve the Gomti River for future generations, it is essential to address these environmental concerns through improved waste management, better regulation of livestock activities, and promoting sustainable tourism practices. Collaboration between local authorities and communities will be crucial in ensuring the long-term health of the river, maintaining its crucial role in the economy, and safeguarding its natural environment. Properly managing the river's resources will ensure that it continues to serve as a vital source of life and livelihood for Lucknow's residents.

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Conflicts of interest

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